

IDENTIFICATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES IN STUDENTS AT THE EARLY STAGE IN TECHNOLOGY LESSONS

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Abstract: this article discusses the issues of identifying and developing the creative activity of students in technology lessons. The article gives a broad concept of creativity as such. The rationale for the importance of technology lessons in the development of students' creative abilities is given. It also describes how to achieve the task.

Key words: creativity, creative abilities, ability, creative activity, creative thinking

The intensive development of science, the emergence of computing and computer technology, advanced technologies have significantly changed the environment of the individual. At the same time, the introduction of complex technical devices into the production process, living environment, communications, transport, medicine, education, etc. cover not only the political, economic, social structures of society surrounding a person, but also the person himself.

From these positions, society needs specialists who have flexible and creative thinking, who are able to freely navigate in a rapidly changing world and adapt to it, who know how to transform the surrounding reality. Consequently, creative activity and the ability of the individual to search for and create something new, as well as the desire for a productive solution of urgent tasks and problems, acquires relevance.

One of the most important tasks of modern education, associated with the need to increase the intellectual potential of society, is the development of activity, mobility and creative activity of a person.

As you know, creativity is a human activity aimed at creating some new, original product in the field of science, art, technology and production. The creative

process is always a breakthrough into the unknown, but it is preceded by a long accumulation of experience, knowledge, skills and abilities, it is characterized by the transition of the number of all kinds of ideas and approaches into a new peculiar quality.

Abilities are such psychological characteristics of a person on which the success of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities depends, but which themselves cannot be reduced to the presence of this knowledge, skills and abilities.

The concept of "creativity" is considered by various sciences, each of which introduces its own specifics into the definition of this category. In different historical epochs, the answer to the question of creativity was interpreted differently. From ancient philosophy to the present day creativity is seen as the "creator of history", artistic creativity, art in the broadest sense of the word, action, the foundations of knowledge, reflections on the unconscious nature of creativity, subject-practical activity, invention, a combination of ideas leading to a solution of a problem, and disclosure of the aspects of scientific thinking, the so-called "pure science", etc.

Until the middle of the 20th century, no significant importance was attached to the study of creativity, society did not have an urgent need for this kind of research. Then, studies of the effectiveness of creativity, and, above all, scientific, were influenced by the acute vital requirements of society. The foundations of these conditions were generated by a qualitative leap in the development of productive forces.

A.G.Spirkin notes that modern philosophy is characterized by a parallel interpretation of creativity, on the one hand, as a purely intellectual phenomenon, on the other hand, as an existential phenomenon that underlies the freedom of the individual.[1]

Products of creativity are discovery and invention. In the process of creativity, not only new objects appear, but the development of the essential forces of a person takes place, he transforms not only the external environment, but also himself. Full-fledged creativity does not mean that a person has interesting ideas, topics, but that

these ideas are embodied in an appropriate product that becomes the property of society, accessible to perception, understanding and evaluation of other people. It follows that significant shifts in the knowledge of the patterns of creative activity are especially relevant at the stage of development of society, when creativity in all areas of social production activity becomes a necessary condition for further socio-economic progress.

Thus, creative activity is considered by us as "an activity that contributes to the development of a whole range of qualities of a creative person", mental activity, ingenuity and finesse, the desire to acquire knowledge necessary to perform specific practical work, independence in choosing and solving a problem, diligence, the ability to see the main thing. This means that a creative person is a person who has mastered such an activity. A creative personality is born when students learn to independently apply their previously acquired knowledge, are able to imagine the object in question, compare with others, draw conclusions, express their attitude to the object.

In order to purposefully develop creative thinking in students, it is first necessary to clearly understand the main features of creative activity that must be formed in students throughout the entire period of schooling. This issue was most thoroughly studied by I.Ya.Lerner who identified the following procedural features of creative activity, the acquisition of which is sufficient as an initial basis for its further development and deepening [2]:

1. independent transfer of knowledge and skills to a new situation;
2. vision of new problems in familiar, standard conditions;
3. vision of a new possible function of a familiar object;
4. vision of the structure of the object to be studied (for example, vision of the composition of the conditions of the problem, the types of its data, the nature of their relationship with the requirement);
5. the ability to see an alternative solution, an alternative approach to its search;

6. the ability to combine previously known methods of solving a problem to design a new method;
7. the ability to create an original way with the fame of others.

The listed features represent an approximate basis for the experience of creative activity that schoolchildren should master. This basis is common to all areas of scientific and applied creativity (with the exception of various types of artistic creativity, for which these features are not enough). Having mastered this foundation, students receive a basis for further self-development, they will be able to develop the appropriate intellectual properties to a level due to natural inclinations and diligence.

M.N.Skatkin writes that “It is necessary to start the purposeful development of creative thinking as early as possible so as not to miss the very rich opportunities of childhood”. The author emphasizes that it is possible to form these intellectual properties only by including schoolchildren in creative activities that are within their power and require the manifestation of one or another of the above features. Manifested in the solution of creative, problematic tasks, these features are formed in the process of their solution.[3]

The development of the creative abilities of schoolchildren has now acquired great social significance. Our society needs not just competent workers-performers, but specialists who perform work quickly, efficiently, beautifully, creatively. Creative people quickly adapt in society, at work, better master the profession and do their job. Creative potentials are inherent and exist in every person. Under favorable conditions, every child can express himself. Creativity is, first of all, the ability to abandon stereotypes of thinking, only in this case you can create something new.[4]

At the first technology lessons, in most cases, you can see that children practically do not know how to fantasize or are afraid of it, although every child has enough inherent creative potential. It just takes a little help to open them up. From

this we can conclude: it is necessary to build technology lessons so that every child feels like a genius, can be realized as a creative person.

One of the pedagogical tasks today is the introduction into the educational process of such developing technologies that help students not only acquire certain knowledge, skills and abilities in a particular field of activity, but also develop their creative potential. And, of course, an important role in the implementation of these tasks is assigned to the lessons of technology. Practice shows that for a teacher the task of developing students' creative abilities is the most difficult and difficult task to implement. That is why correctly chosen educational technologies help the teacher to determine the possible extent of students' involvement in creative activities, which makes learning interesting within the curriculum. [5]

The subject "Technology" is a creative subject that provides great opportunities for educating a creative, versatile personality. After all, to develop the creative abilities of a person is first of all to cultivate a creative attitude to work. At the same time, the labor is considered as a source of formation of cognitive activity, an independent attitude to the task. A creative attitude to work is both the upbringing of love for the work and the desire to know its features, which in turn stimulate them to try their hand and achieve success. In the process of a creative attitude to work, such valuable qualities as perseverance, curiosity, purposefulness, initiative, independence, the ability to choose the best way and method of doing work are developed, i.e. those qualities without which creativity is impossible. Based on the tasks set, the following ideas can be expressed:

- 1) creativity must and can be taught;
- 2) creativity is not a natural quality of the mind.

The development of creative abilities in students can be implemented based on the following principles:

- 1) the principle of development of motivation for creative activity;
- 2) the principle of developing the skills of self-education and self-education;
- 3) the principle of priority of creative activity;

- 4) the principle of harmonization of the pedagogical process and the individual characteristics of students;
- 5) the principle of choosing forms of education that ensure the independence and creativity of students.

The modern lesson of technology is marked by the breadth of learning objectives. In addition to equipping students with a system of knowledge and skills, upbringing, personal development, creative thinking, and teaching methods of independent activity are now coming to the fore.

It should be noted that the creative and developmental nature of specialized technology education is ensured by the use of information tools, heuristic and algorithmic methods for solving inventive problems, self-analysis of the product of creative work, and presentation of the results of project activities. [6]

Based on the above, we can conclude that the development of students' creative activity in technology lessons should be and is a necessary, organized process, which was not observed in previous periods of school formation.

References:

1. Спиркин А.Г. Философия. Учебник для ВУЗов. М. 2006 г.
2. Лернер И.Я. Проблемное обучение. М.,1974, с.12-16
3. Скаткин М.Н. Школа и всесторонне развитие детей. М.,1980.-с.33
4. Хаецкая Е. А. Развитие и выявление индивидуальных особенностей детей. Развитие творческой инициативы. Донецк. 2016 г.
5. Миронова И.В. Развитие творческих способностей на уроках технологии. 2016 г
6. Амосков В.М. Условия развития умений творческо-поисковой деятельности учащихся при изучении образовательной области «Технология» [Текст] / Амосков В.М. // Вестник Новгородского Государственного Университета имени Ярослава Мудрого, 2007 №40, - С. 16-18